

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Bankability Reports

Deliverable 5.5

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0 Executive summary

This executive summary outlines the critical need for scaled-up climate adaptation finance, drawing insights from the TransformAr project's bankability reports, made for the six European demonstrator regions of TransformAr. It highlights existing barriers to private investment in adaptation solutions and proposes innovative financial and governance mechanisms to overcome these challenges, demonstrating pathways towards bankability.

The escalating risks and damages from climate change necessitate an urgent increase in adaptation solutions, yet a significant gap persists between required resources and current financial flows. Traditional public financing, often in the form of grants, has dominated the adaptation market, leading to limited engagement with the private sector for repayable capital. To address this, a "business model approach" or "bankability" framework is crucial, emphasizing a blended mix of public and private resources. The report mainly serves as framework and methodological guide for exploring alternative financing solutions and is conceptually applied to the six demonstrators of TransformAr. Once more robust data becomes available, the methodology can be applied quantitatively.

Bankability is defined as a project's ability to attract investors and lenders willing to finance or fund its costs, with a clear expectation of refundability and return on investment. Unlike traditional projects with evident returns (e.g., real estate rent), climate adaptation solutions, particularly nature-based solutions (NBS), often lack clear revenue streams, hindering private investment. This report explores how to attract private investors by examining two types:

- traditional financial institutions (banks, insurers, pension funds, asset managers) that seek return on investment and increasingly consider Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) criteria, and
- direct/indirect beneficiaries of adaptation solutions (local businesses, citizens) who may invest based on direct positive impacts or avoided costs.

The TransformAr project employs two primary approaches to develop bankability reports for its adaptation solutions:

1) Type 1: scaling pilot projects (reports 1, 2 and 3)

For projects tested at a smaller scale, bankability reports explore financing/funding options to expand and accelerate their implementation. This approach typically follows a five-step methodological framework covering system outputs, stakeholder involvement (providers and beneficiaries), cost-benefit estimation (monetary, when the data was available, otherwise non-monetary), financial arrangement development (financing and funding instruments), and risk identification.

2) Type 2: strengthening collaborative networks (reports 4, 5 and 6)

For solutions focused on established governance networks, bankability reports support attracting private investment for long-term financial sustainability. This involves analyzing barriers and opportunities through stakeholder interviews, exploring alternative financing/funding arrangements (based on international case studies), and finally outlining calls to action. This type did not include quantitative analysis.

The summary of the 6 bankability reports is made in the table below:

<i>Annex n°</i>	<i>Region</i>	<i>Financial model components researched</i>
1	Lappeenranta, Finland	Adaptation solution: Stormwater management measures Funded by water tariffs, carbon credits, taxes, retributions, avoided costs

		Financed using green bonds, PPS, blended finance
2	Egaleo, Greece	Adaptation solution: Greening schoolyards and schoolbuildings Funded by avoided costs, taxes and retributions Financing by “as-a-service” contracts, municipal green bond,
3	Galicia, Spain	Adaptation solution: Mussel raft monitoring system Funded by blended co-financing model OR payment for ecosystem data
4	West Country Region, UK	Adaptation solution: Nature based solutions on farmland Exploring the implementation of a nutrient credit trading scheme to fund nature based solutions on farmland Explore the use of Payment for exosystem services, de-risking strategies and environmental impact bonds
5	Oristano, Italy	Adaptation solution: nature conservancy Funding by payment for ecosystem services, reward-based crowdfunding Financing by adaptation bond and governance by integrated water management governance structure
6	Guadeloupe, France	Adaptation solutions in tourism and agriculture Pooling funds using the Climate Adaptation Fund of Guadeloupe (FLAG) Attract additional private finance by using support tools like a sustainability framework, AI, smart contracts

Overall, the bankability reports indicate that while integrating bankability early in solution development, it helps to identify additional beneficiaries and diverse revenue streams. Involving private investors often faces apprehension due to a lack of knowledge, capacity, and the perception that adaptation solutions are solely public goods. Many demonstrators operate on a project-by-project basis, limiting the scale needed to attract large institutional investors, though local community involvement can be a viable alternative. Data availability for detailed cost and benefit estimations remains a challenge, suggesting that bankability considerations should be integrated at the outset of adaptation planning.

1 Introduction

1.1 The adaptation finance gap

As risks and damages are increasing due to climate change and extreme weather it is becoming more urgent to scale-up the implementation of adaptation solutions to address rising impacts. However, there is a huge gap between necessary resources to sufficiently become adaptive, and the current public financial flows towards adaptation solutions (UNEP, 2024). According to the "Is Europe on track towards climate resilience?" report by the European Environment Agency (EEA, 2023), EU Member States have made progress in their national adaptation actions. The report highlights that EU funds play a significant role in financing adaptation actions for most Member States, with €26 billion budgeted for climate adaptation funding for the period 2021-2027. However, a lack of financing remains an important barrier hindering the implementation of adaptation solutions. Moreover, in 2023 the EIB published their 'Investing in Nature-based Solutions' report (European Investment, Hudson, Hart, & Verbeek, 2023), in which they highlight that the adaptation solution market, specifically the market for nature-based solutions, is dominated by grant funding, leading few entities to engage with the private sector for repayable capital. This gap has sparked an emerging conversation in the literature (Biasin, Toxopeus, Pettenella, Polzin, & Masiero, 2024; den Heijer & Coppens, 2023; Dorst et al., 2022; Mayor et al., 2021; Papari, Toxopeus, Polzin, Bulkeley, & Menguzzo, 2024; Toxopeus & Polzin, 2021) and other EU-supported projects (Invest4Nature, ClimateFIT, Pathways2Resilience, PIISA, Naturance...) on how to develop alternative financing possibilities including private financing.

1.2 What is bankability?

Attracting private financing to develop adaptation solutions is particularly challenging, as most adaptation solutions can be characterized as public goods, making public financing the most logical route (Toxopeus & Polzin, 2021). To demonstrate the added value of climate adaptation solutions, scholars and practitioners are increasingly employing a 'business model approach' (den Heijer & Coppens, 2023; Mayor et al., 2021) or an approach describing the 'bankability' of a project, referring to blended financing in which a creative mix of public and private resources is achieved (McCoy & Schwartz, 2023). In these approaches diverse mechanisms and instruments are considered to attract or unlock additional private resources.

In general terms bankability can be defined as *the ability of a project to attract parties (investors, lenders) prepared to finance or fund for (part of) the project cost*. In which **financing** refers to the **provision of resources needed to implement** a project, and **funding** refers to the **ultimate payment of the implementation**, operation, and capital costs. Bankability of projects is usually linked to refundability and an expected return on investment by private investors and lenders (McCoy & Schwartz, 2023; WWF, 2020).

For classical investment projects (e.g. real estate), the expected return on investment is evident (e.g. the rent tenants pay). However, solutions for climate change adaptation, e.g. nature-based solutions, are underfunded, and private investments are sought after. Yet, unclarity on the return on investment from adaptation solutions halts private investment. In this report, and the bankability report developed for each of the demonstrators, the bankability of adaptation solutions is explored using the following guiding question: **'How can we attract private investors to support climate change adaptation solutions?'**

2 Identifying private investors

In this section we identify two types of private investors to attract as potential partners in developing adaptation solutions. The first type of investors are traditional **financial institutions**, often working at a European or global (holding) level, such as banks, insurance companies, asset managers, pension funds...

The second type of potential private investors are linked to the fact that adaptation solutions are inherently local, place-based and dependent on the context (Karl et al., 2012). This gives rise to spatial relations linked to adaptation solutions, leading to **direct and indirect beneficiaries**, who we consider as a second group of potential private investors.

2.1 Financial institutions

Financial institutions are described here as investors primarily using debt-financing mechanisms which generate a return on investment. Institutions such as banks, insurance companies, pension funds, asset managers,... typically base investment decisions on technological or financial assessment criteria, e.g. security, profit margin, cashflow potential and risk-sharing structure (Canilao, 2017; Hampl, Lüdeke-Freund, Flink, Olbert, & Ade, 2011; Rada, 2017; Rina consulting, 2019; UAntwerpen, 2021; WWF, 2020; Zhu & Chua, 2018) to assess whether they want to invest in a project. In recent years the sustainability of investments is under increasing scrutiny due to public pressure (Yang & Wang, 2024), encouraging investors to take environmental, social and governance (ESG) criteria into account as additional investment criteria. In a climate change adaptation context, ESG criteria include, e.g. the increase in the resilience of ecosystems and communities, increased biodiversity, alignment with national adaptation priorities (Ellis & Pillay, 2017; World Bank, 2019). Additionally, European legislation such as Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFRD), Non-Financial Reporting Directive (and Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive, CSRD) and the EU Taxonomy, provides investors with frameworks to report on the sustainability of their investments.

In 'D5.3 Understanding Investment Opportunities: Workshops with future solution buyers', interviews were held with EU-level financial institutions, providing insights in the bankability potential of climate adaptation solutions.

2.2 Direct and indirect beneficiaries of adaptation solutions

Effects of adaptation solutions, such as nature-based solutions or technological and digital solutions, lead to benefits which will be experienced directly, or indirectly. Adaptation benefits will vary, depending on the type of solutions, its spatial application and the spatial relation between 'solution' area and 'benefit' area (Schirpke, Scolozzi, De Marco, & Tappeiner, 2014). When introducing a new green space in an urban setting as adaptation solution, those who live in proximity to the green space will benefit more (e.g. shading, cooling, recreational options, value increase of real estate...) than those who live farther away. They will **directly** benefit.

Simultaneously, the new green space could provide extra stormwater infiltration and buffering opportunities reducing pollution due to combined sewage overflow (if designed as such), providing **indirect** benefits to utility companies, such as wastewater treatment plants, and river managers. Each adaptation solution will have a specific spatial range, related to a variety of ecosystem services, possibly both ecological and economic, which will produce beneficiaries at local, regional, or even national level (Schirpke et al., 2014). These beneficiaries can be categorized into various groups; (local) government, public institutions (such as schools or hospitals), non-government organization or civil society, (local) businesses (or for-profit companies), research institutions and universities, citizens and vulnerable communities (Cooper, Cunningham, & Bracken, 2023).

Investments from beneficiaries will be based on different assessments to those used by institutional investors. Beneficiaries are more likely to favor positive impacts (e.g. in their neighborhood) provided by the adaptation solutions, as opposed to requiring a return on investment. The climate solutions developed within TransformAr were co-created within key community systems stakeholder groups, by taking beneficiaries (both direct and indirect) into account. We consider a more community-focused approach to attracting private investors (e.g. user-pays schemes, crowdlending, volunteering,

philanthropy,...). In the bankability reports we explore whether beneficiaries of climate adaptation solutions can be involved as ‘private investors’ in developing bankable projects.

3 Research methodology

The demonstrators developed five types of adaptation solutions during TransformAr; (1) behavioural change and awareness raising, (2) governance schemes, (3) nature based solutions, (4) technological and digital solutions and (5) financial, economic and insurance schemes. Solutions classified in the type 1, 2 and 4 are designed to support monitoring and decision-making, rather than to directly generate investable, revenue-generating assets or infrastructures. These solutions are designed to influence adaptation action design based on the interpretation of data, aligning decision-making, or creating awareness in the broader public. As such, their financial return pathways are less direct, and their value lies in enabling or informing adaptation rather than constituting adaptation actions themselves. Solutions developed in type 3, e.g. constructed wetlands in the West Country Region, are pilot projects and have been financed by the investment budget of TransformAr itself. Type 5, The financial, economic and insurance solutions will be further elaborated upon in the bankability reports of the associated demonstrators.

In the bankability reports the focus lies on developing financial schemes attracting private financing to invest in ‘adaptation infrastructure’. As not all demonstrators have developed infrastructure which requires investment, a first step was defining the scope of ‘bankability’ for each demonstrator and considering the role for private financing. An overview of the solutions developed within each demonstrator is provided below in table 1, including a short description of the solution explored in the demonstrator bankability reports. A more detailed description of the TransformAr solutions can be found in D6.3 “*Catalogue of Solutions*” on the [TransformAr website](#).

Table 1 Overview of TransformAr solutions developed by the demonstrators and solutions further developed in the bankability reports

Demonstrator	TransformAr Solutions	Solutions further developed in the bankability report
Lappeenranta (FI)	Citizen App (CAF), NBS for urban stormwater management (URB), Stormwater Management System (SWM), Digital Monitoring (SWMM), Choice Experiment for investors (CEI)	NBS for stormwater management (URB), with other solutions such as Choice experiment for investors (CEI) supporting the development of the bankability report
Egaleo (GR)	Citizen App (CAE), Awareness raising and behavioural change modules (AWAR), Climate Innovation Hub (CIH), Smart Climate stations (SCS)	A future NBS solution (schoolyard greening) is explored in the bankability report, as a possible development scenario, based on the solutions Awareness raising and behavioural change modules (AWAR) and Smart Climate Stations (SCS).
Galicia region (ES)	Resilience Index (RI), Mussel Raft Monitoring (MRM), Intertidal Monitoring (INTERM)	Attracting private investment for Mussel Raft Monitoring (MRM) is explored in the bankability report.
Oristano province (IT)	Coastal contracts (COAST), Smart Grid for coastal management (SG)	Attracting private financing to support the governance scheme of the Coastal contract (COAST) is examined in the bankability report.

Guadeloupe (FR)	Nudging (NUDG), Adaptation Fund (AF)	The Adaptation Fund (AF) was developed as a financial solution. In the bankability report, instruments for attracting additional private financing for this solution is explored.
West Country Region (UK)	Integrated Constructed Wetlands (ICW), ICW Monitoring (ICWM), Green Bonds (GB)	In the UK, the nutrient credit scheme provides the background for the various solutions. In the bankability report, the opportunities and barriers related to the nutrient credit scheme and the impacts on developing nature-based solutions such as integrated constructed wetlands are discussed.

As the bankability reports were developed towards the end of the TransformAr project their scope is exploratory in nature. The goal of the bankability reports is to provide insight, inspire and form a starting point from which discussions can be held with necessary stakeholders regarding the bankability of the demonstrators' climate adaptation solutions. Additionally, many new stakeholders have been identified in the bankability reports, based on the principle of involving beneficiaries, who were previously not involved in the discussions. In this sense the bankability reports should be read as a starting point of an ongoing conversation on the financing of implementation of adaptation solutions. The reports aim to encourage the demonstrators to engage in the network of adaptation beneficiaries and financiers of their solution and in their region.

3.1 Two approaches towards developing a bankability report

Each of the developed climate adaptation solutions within the demonstrators are at different stages of the process from plan-making to implementation, and monitoring, which is best described as an iterative process. In the Regional Adaptation Support Tool¹ 6 guiding steps are identified for moving from policy development to implementation and monitoring:

- Step 1: Preparing the ground for adaptation
- Step 2: Assessing climate risks and vulnerabilities
- Step 3: Identifying adaptation options
- Step 4: Assessing and selecting adaptation options
- Step 5: Implementing adaptation policies and actions
- Step 6: Monitoring, evaluation and learning

Funding is mentioned in this framework in step 1.4 'Identifying Resources' and step 5.3 'Securing Funding or Financing'. Step 1.4 encourages the project manager to identify and evaluate diverse financing and funding options early on in the project. In step 5.3, it is encouraged to couple the estimated implementation and maintenance cost to a specific financing stakeholder, using a designated (set of) instrument(s). However, the TransformAr climate adaptation solutions demonstrate that bankability can and should be considered at all steps of this iterative process, as a **supporting tool in transformational adaptation**. Each of the demonstrators followed their own timeline with adaptation solutions being at different stages of development. Bankability at different steps throughout the development can be considered a valuable tool to assist in **scaling-up and accelerating** the implementation of solutions.

In 'D6.4 Guidance document on transformational adaptation', transformational adaptation is described, as opposed to incremental adaptation, as entailing profound changes that alter the fundamental structures of systems to better respond to the long-term impacts of climate change (Watkiss & Cimato,

¹ Developed by Climate Adapt, more information can be found here: <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/knowledge-and-data/regional-adaptation-support-tool>

2020). Instead of focusing on preserving the status quo, transformational adaptation envisions new pathways for development, addressing underlying vulnerabilities and inequalities while preparing for future uncertainties (Chu et al., 2019). It requires shifts across systems rather than within them. These changes aim for more open-ended outcomes and involve planned management, often necessitating a radical shift in practices and governance (Lonsdale, Pringle, & Turner, 2015).

Within transformational adaptation, the financial system is an important underlying structure that can significantly influence adaptation outcomes. A financial system favouring grey-infrastructure solutions over nature-based solutions will need to be redesigned, if this is the preferred adaptation solution. The Copenhagen Cloudburst Management Plan forms an excellent example to illustrate this point, as the regulatory rules regarding water tariffs in Denmark needed to be reassessed to be able to include nature-based solutions as infrastructural investment². Designing supporting financial systems to be aligned with envisioned adaptation solution outcomes is thus a crucial consideration when developing transformational adaptation solutions.

Within this framework of transformational adaptation, and the supporting role financial systems play on desired adaptation outcomes, two approaches have been identified to developing adaptation solutions within TransformAr, in which bankability serves two different roles:

- In the **first approach** to developing adaptation solutions pilot-projects play a significant role, in which adaptation solutions are tested at a smaller scale to develop lessons learned to subsequently scale-up. These solutions are more project/product oriented. The role of a bankability report in this context is to **explore financing/funding options to scale-up the developed solutions and accelerate their implementation.**
 - o Approach identified in demonstrators: Lappeenranta, Galicia region and Egaleo
- In a **second approach**, the focus has been much more on developing strong collaborative governance networks in which adaptation solutions are co-created and developed. These solutions are oriented towards collaboratively collecting (including attracting private financing/funding) and allocating resources. In this approach bankability reports serve a **supporting role, to further strengthen the collaborative governance networks and the implementation of adaptation solutions:**
 - o Approach identified in demonstrators: Guadeloupe, Oristano and West-Country region

Considering the different roles a bankability report can serve, and considering that the bankability reports are tailor made to best fit the adaptation solutions and governance context of each demonstrator, we have developed two guiding frameworks for the bankability reports, which is outlined in the next section.

3.1.1 Type 1: Moving from pilot-projects to scaling-up and accelerating transformational adaptation

The framework was set-up holistically to consider the bankability of the adaptation solutions. The framework draws inspiration from various other guiding documents, such as the Sustainable Asset Valuation (SAVi)³ developed by the International Institute for Sustainable Development. As this framework was developed by spatial planners, there is a much larger focus on spatial-relational and socio-institutional aspects, as opposed to a focus on determining the exact costs, benefits and quantitative valuation. Furthermore, the framework is considered as guiding (as opposed to rigid), as each of the

² More information on this case can be found here: <https://climatefit-heu.eu/best-practices/03-cloudburst-management-plan/>

³ <https://www.iisd.org/projects/sustainable-asset-valuation-savi>

bankability reports was tailor-made to suite the demonstrator context. The 5 overarching steps used to develop the bankability reports are outlined in Figure 2 and explained below;

Figure 1 Methodological framework for type 1 bankability reports (illustrated by author).

1. A first step consists of understanding how the transformational adaptation solution(s) will impact the existing situation, more specifically which **system inputs and outcomes** will be transformed and to what extent. This is based on developed adaptation targets, for example reducing pollution caused by urban run-off, or reducing heat-stress. Additionally, any co-benefits that a certain strategy might entail, such as biodiversity co-benefits from nature-based solutions, are identified and included in the bankability analysis.
2. The second step consists of two parts;
 - **Identifying provider:** identifying who needs to provide or implement the proposed adaption solutions. Adaptation solutions are often a spatial issue, which means they will need to be implemented on someone's property, either public or private. Property rights are thus often an important aspect when implementing a solution. Adaptation solutions are often integrated solutions, however, the public or private entities who need to implement them may not have aligned ambitions and/or competencies, leading to a siloed approach. This can lead to multi-level, multi-governance, multi-sector challenges when implementing solutions. Identifying the 'providers' early on also aids in determining who will need to be involved within the decision-making process.
 - **Identifying beneficiaries:** Benefits identified during the first step can vary in nature, as they can be perceived as public, private, club or common pool goods generating varying beneficiaries. Depending on the context, the beneficiaries will vary, but identifying them early on will help determine which (financial) instruments could be used to capture the benefits.

3. Third step is estimating the costs and benefits;
 - **Costs:** Identifying what the costs of transformation will be, accounting for both capital investment costs of implementing the solution, and operational costs to maintain the solutions over time. Costs can be estimated based on quotes or reference projects. Additionally in some cases the cost of inaction (or not implementing adaptation solutions) is also taken into account, this will be done based on 'D2.3 Review of economic evaluations of CC, productivity losses and damage assessments for KCS' and 'D2.4 Climate-cost-assessment'.
 - **Benefits:** Benefits of adaptation solutions can be both monetary and non-monetary, both are taken into account. Monetary benefits are further described as an '**avoided cost**', or as '**added benefit**', which can provide an additional revenue stream. Avoided costs are understood as a monetization of the benefits arising from the protection that adaptation solutions provide and protects from the harm that would occur in its absence. This content is supported by 'D3.4 Tools on the avoided damages and benefits per demo'. Added benefits, which can produce additional revenue streams, are understood as the creation of value that was not there before the implementation of the adaptation solution. Environmental economists have developed dozens of valuation methods to estimate these benefits, where possible they will be applied. The non-monetary value of certain adaptation solutions, even though they might not contribute to the financial model, will still be an important part of the valuation, especially towards governments or local beneficiaries interested in investing in adaptation solutions generating local impacts.

4. In Step 4, financing and funding instruments are explored to both capture benefits and incentivize 'providers'. The steps can be seen as iterative, depending on the necessary alterations to find the correct balance;
 - **Financing:** To develop the adaptation solutions in some demonstrators an upfront investment may be necessary to finance the adaptation solution infrastructure, before benefits can be captured (e.g. a park will provide benefits once it is realized and not before). In this step we consider financing instruments based on the costs (*step 3*) and the provider of the adaptation infrastructure (*step 2*). This step is context dependent as existing regulatory frameworks may hinder the use of certain financial instruments (e.g. not all municipalities can issue green bonds). Additionally, the cost plays an important role as well, especially when wanting to attract financial institutions as private investors. Financial institutions can require a significant scale of investment (e.g. upwards of ca. 1 million), which may not always be suitable for certain adaptation solutions. In some demonstrators where less investments are needed, funding-based mechanisms, such as payment-for-ecosystem services, may be more suitable.
 - **Funding:** Estimating benefits will help identify a monetary revenue stream which can be captured by additional funding instruments. These instruments need to be introduced, or existing instruments need to be altered, to capture the revenue stream. Which instruments can be employed is context specific based on socio-cultural, -institutional and political aspects. Benefit capturing instruments can be fiscal instruments such as additional taxes or levies directed at beneficiaries (e.g. tourist taxes, developer obligation,...), or urban planning instruments such as planning regulations (zoning requirements) or permit requirements for new or existing developments, stimulating private investment in adaptation solutions on private property (e.g. increased stormwater measures on private property can unburden municipalities to invest in public

stormwater measures). Identifying these funding instruments and determining which ‘beneficiaries’ they target is an important step, as this will become the funding stream of the adaptation solutions.

5. The final step consists of matching both the financing and funding instruments in a time-suitable arrangement aligned with the development of the adaptation solution, and identifying the risks;
 - a. Matching financing and funding: Depending on certain preconditions or local preferences financing can be obtained through debt or equity, a combination of both or can be funded by available budgets, either public, private or combined. Lending capacity will also strongly be determined by funding capacity. Additionally, depending on which instruments are employed, ‘time’ also needs to be taken into consideration, as certain adaptation benefits will only develop after a period of time (e.g. restoring an ecosystem takes time, so related benefits can only be captured after completion). Furthermore some instruments may capture benefits in a predictable way (e.g. taxation), while others will be more unpredictable and vary each year (e.g. developer obligations). Finding the right rhythm between these different systems and aligning this to the development and maintenance/monitoring of the adaptation solution is therefore a crucial last step to the bankability puzzle.
 - b. Iteratively identifying uncertainties and risks: Making predictions is never without risk, throughout each of the steps assumptions are made or modeled. Although risks are considered iteratively throughout the development of the bankability reports, in this final step an overview is provided to help determine the feasibility of the proposed scheme and introduce risk mitigating measures if necessary.

3.1.2 Type 2: Developing strong collaborative networks as a foundation for financing implementation

The second type of bankability reports are aimed at serving a supporting role, to further strengthen existing funding and financing solutions and existing collaborative governance networks. The reports serve to attract additional private investment to ensure financial sustainability over a longer period of time. These reports are subdivided into three sections; the first part analyses the barriers and opportunities of funding and financing solutions that are currently being tested in the region. This is done by gaining insight in the perceptions of local financial stakeholder. The second part explores alternative financing/funding arrangements or supporting (digital) infrastructure for attracting private parties in the financial solutions. The third part contains a call to action, outlining how demonstrators can further develop their solutions.

1. Barriers and opportunities

Some demonstratos have passed the stage of piloting their adaptation solution; they have experience in applying their adaptation solutions and/or a have a solid stakeholder network, but often still heavily rely on public budgets or grants (EU, national or regional grants). To continue further accelerate their adaption solutions, they aim to leverage their collaboration and available the public funds, to further attract private investments. However, effective engagement with private investors requires tailored policies, incentives and partnerships, whether it is directed at financial institutes or beneficiaries of the adaptation solutions.

To better understand the perceptions of financial stakeholders, the demonstrators performed in-depth interviews with investors uncovering the perceived barriers and opportunities to further accelerate the

implementation of the adaptation solutions. The barriers and opportunities were divided in five categories. Table 2 shows the five categories and provides examples of a barrier and opportunity for every category.

Table 2. Five Categories of barriers and opportunities for private involvement in adaptation finance, experienced by stakeholders involved in the demonstrator projects (type 2).

Category	Examples of barriers	Examples of opportunities
Public sector governance	debt ceilings and state aid regulation	Blended finance tools
Private sector governance	risk aversion	Public guarantees
Economy	short term capital needs	Debt financing
Skills & knowledge	lack of data sharing	Shared platforms for data access
Socio-cultural aspects	culture of 'status quo'	Demonstration of successes

2. Exploring alternative funding/financing instruments

Based on the results of the interviews, the second part of the report discusses the current use and future potential of alternative funding/financing instruments and corresponding governance instruments. Existing exemplary cases are used to illustrate the potential of these instruments. This part of the bankability report sets-out a variation of possible pathways to further attract private investment, tailored to the context of the demonstrator and the adaptation solution.

3. Call to action

This final part of the bankability report presents a framework identifying possible steps forward. tap into the opportunities mentioned. This final call to action aims to help demonstrators tackle the first steps in involving private investors in developing their adaptation solutions.

3.2 Process

The bankability reports were iteratively developed in collaboration with the demonstrators in workshops held during Consortium Meeting 7 (sept 2024) and 8 (april 2025), in which UA provided a guiding framework, and demonstrators provided insight in their local context and delivered feedback on results. Table 3 provides an overview of how the process helped shape the final bankability reports, outlining the process of collaboration between UA, demonstrators and local stakeholders.

Table 3 Overview of process in which bankability reports were collaboratively developed between UA, demonstrators and local stakeholders

Timing	Objective	Partners
Jun – Juli 2024	Discussions on preliminary idea of bankability and data availability	UA & demonstrators
Sept 2024	Workshop with demonstrators providing insight in bankability methodology, discussion of examples, and identification of relevant local stakeholders to include in interviews.	UA & demonstrators

Dec – Feb 2025	Demonstrator Interviews with relevant local stakeholders	Demonstrators
Feb 2025	Synthesis of results	UA
April 2025	Identifying challenges & opportunities, feedback on interviews with international investment organizations, and validation of bankability reports.	UA & Demonstrators
April – May 2025	Demonstrator led consultation workshops with involved stakeholders about bankability reports	Demonstrators
May 2025	Synthesis of results	UA

4 Results

The result of this deliverable are 6 bankability reports, one for every demo region in TransformAr. The reports are added as separate reports in the Annex. The overview of the resulting bankability reports in given in table 4. A summary of every report is given in the subsections here.

Table 4. The results of this deliverable are 6 bankability reports

Annex n°	Region	Financial model components researched
1	Lappeenranta, Finland	Adaptation solution: Stormwater management measures Funded by water tariffs, carbon credits, taxes, retributions, avoided costs Financed using green bonds, PPS, blended finance
2	Egaleo, Greece	Adaptation solution: Greening schoolyards and schoolbuildings Funded by avoided costs, taxes and retributions Financing by “as-a-service” contracts, municipal green bond,
3	Galicia, Spain	Adaptation solution: Mussel raft monitoring system Funded by blended co-financing model OR payment for ecosystem data
4	West Country Region, UK	Adaptation solution: Nature based solutions on farmland Exploring the implementation of a nutrient credit trading scheme to fund nature based solutions on farmland Explore the use of Payment for exosystem services, de-risking strategies and environmental impact bonds
5	Oristano, Italy	Adaptation solution: nature conservancy Funding by payment for ecosystem serices, reward-based crowdfunding Financing by adaptation bond and governance by integrated water management governance structure

6	Guadeloupe, France	Adaptation solutions in tourism and agriculture Pooling funds using the Climate Adaptation Fund of Guadeloupe (FLAG) Attract additional private finance by using support tools like a sustainability framework, AI, smart contracts
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4.1 Type 1: Moving from pilot-projects to scaling-up and accelerating transformational adaptation

4.1.1 Bankability report Lappeenranta

This bankability report for Lappeenranta, Finland, investigates financial opportunities for implementing Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) in public spaces and on private plots to mitigate risks from heavy rainfall, flooding, and nutrient overload in Lake Saimaa. The report focuses on retention and infiltration NBS in public areas and stormwater management measures, including green roofs, on private plots. The City of Lappeenranta and private property owners are the primary implementers, with beneficiaries including property owners, insurance companies, the publicly-owned water company (Lappeenrannan Energia), and tourism businesses. An initial investment of €20 million is considered, to scale-up the implementation of public NBS to cover 5,2 hectares. Monetized benefits include reduced flood damages, reduced water sanitation costs, carbon sequestration and increased property values. Proposed funding instruments include an NBS risk reduction fund (from insurers), carbon credits, a stormwater purification fund (via utility fees or stormwater fees), tourist tax, local business tax/urban payment-for-ecosystems services, and land value capture (e.g., 'betterment tax' or 'developer obligations'). For initial financing, green (impact) bonds and Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) are explored. The report concludes that the investment could be bankable if the city introduces additional levies and taxes and collaborates with insurers. Despite this potential, both public and private parties still perceive NBS, as public goods, as not yet generating clear enough revenue streams.

4.1.2 Bankability report Egaleo

This bankability report explores the financial viability of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) in schoolyards within the Municipality of Egaleo, Greece, aiming to mitigate the impacts of extreme heat and flooding. Proposed NBS include green roofs and the greening of schoolyards with trees and wadis, offering cooling, flood reduction, and socio-economic and environmental benefits. The report identifies stakeholders such as the Municipality of Egaleo, schools (including teachers, students, parents), and the Ministry of Education, Religious Affairs and Sports as providers, and the local community (neighborhood inhabitants, school community) as beneficiaries. Estimated investment costs range from €450,000 to €800,000 for green roofs and €70,000 to €500,000 for schoolyard greening across seven school sites. Monetized benefits include avoided flood damages to properties, reduced water bills (when reusing stormwater), reduced energy bills for cooling, and increased property values of nearby homeowners. Two financial models are discussed: 'As a Service' (also known as performance based) contracts (for water and energy savings) and the issuance of municipal green bonds. The general finding is that NBS are currently perceived as "non-bankable" due to unclear revenue streams, despite generating significant public benefits. The relatively small scale of the projects (€550,000 - €1,300,000) may pose a challenge to attract institutional investors, suggesting the involvement of the local community.

4.1.3 Bankability report Galicia

This bankability report for Galicia examines the attractiveness of the Mussel Raft Monitoring (MRM) system for private financing within the aquaculture sector. The region is exposed to risks such as intense

winter storms, heavy precipitation, and changes in sea temperatures, which affect mussel production. MRM was chosen as the focus in the bankability report due to its provision of real-time, actionable data to individual mussel farmers, enabling direct operational adaptation, such as adjusting harvesting times or mitigating loss. Two financing pathways are proposed: a "blended" co-financing model with public funds and ESG support (Impact Philanthropy) from corporations, and a "Payment-for-Ecosystem Data (PED)" model. In the PED model, mussel supply chain stakeholders (e.g., packaging companies, processors, retailers) pay an annual fee for MRM data access, with funds reinvested into adaptation practices and upstream Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) projects. Costs for the MRM pilot phase were approximately €40,000, with estimated operational costs around €55,000. While quantifying monetary benefits is complex, the value of data for informing adaptive decisions is highly regarded. However, local stakeholders are less familiar with the concept of 'bankability' and perceive climate adaptation as primarily providing public benefits, making it difficult to translate into cashflows.

4.2 Type 2: Accelerating innovative financing solutions by strengthening collaborative networks

4.2.1 Bankability report WRT

The bankability report for the Westcountry Region concludes that Nature-based Solutions (NbS) for climate change adaptation are not yet widely bankable or investable for private investors. This is largely due to uncertain revenue streams from ecosystem services, inconsistent and expensive monitoring and verification requirements, and challenges in accounting for the additionality, attribution, and permanence of these solutions. Specific regional barriers identified include the incompatibility of traditional farm business models, which rely on annual revenue subsidies, with capital investment models suitable for developing credit schemes, as well as a need for regulators to become more willing to depend on NbS. Despite these hurdles, there is a recognized need for urgent investment in climate adaptation, as public funding alone is insufficient to meet the projected costs of climate damages. Opportunities exist to encourage farmer and landowner investment in NbS and Payment for Ecosystem Services (PES) schemes, for example, through peer-to-peer knowledge exchange facilitated by farm clusters, and by providing clearer government guidance on the business tax implications of long-term conservation agreements. The report outlines 14 Calls to Action, including making it easier for utility companies to invest in NbS, developing greater awareness of private sector needs within public and third-sector bodies, de-risking NbS investment projects, exploring innovative financial mechanisms like Environmental Impact Bonds, and establishing reliable, consistent methods for valuing and monitoring ecosystem services to build investor confidence.

4.2.2 Bankability report Oristano

The bankability report for Oristano, Sardinia, highlights that the region faces significant environmental problems, including increased winter storms, heavy precipitation, sea-level rise, and prolonged heatwaves, which endanger agriculture, fishing, tourism, and biodiversity, with sea-level rise alone projected to cause €22 million in annual damages. While public budgets and European grants currently finance wetland conservation, there's a need to attract private investment for adaptation solutions like sustainable agriculture, fishery practices, biodiversity protection, and water level regulation. Key barriers to private involvement include rigid and fragmented public legislative frameworks, a lack of coordination among public entities, an underdeveloped venture capital and impact investing landscape, risk-averse private investors, a conservative banking sector, low financial literacy, a widespread lack of expertise in project development and impact communication, and a cultural reluctance to innovation.

Opportunities exist through national and regional adaptation strategies, EU initiatives providing grants and setting sustainability standards, and public guarantee funds to de-risk private investment. The report proposes several alternative instruments: an Ecosystem Service Credit Program (e.g., Payment for Ecosystem Services for agroforestry) to generate revenue from certified environmental credits for landowners, Reward-Based Crowdfunding to engage the local community for smaller-scale investments, a Local Adaptation Bond to attract private investors (including citizens) for large-scale public green and blue infrastructure, and formalizing the Coastal Contract Fund as a legal entity to pool and strategically allocate resources from various public and private sources. These instruments aim to overcome financial dependence on grants, stimulate private contributions, and ensure long-term financial sustainability for climate resilience in the Gulf of Oristano.

4.2.3 Bankability report Guadeloupe

The bankability report for Guadeloupe reveals that despite facing significant climate change risks like rising sea levels, intense hurricanes, heavy rainfall, and prolonged droughts, its investment capacity is limited due to its status as a French overseas region, which restricts access to certain international funding while also struggling to secure European funds. The Local Adaptation Fund in Guadeloupe (FLAG), initiated by ADEME, aims to pool dispersed public and private funding to address pressing local adaptation needs, acting as a facilitator to harmonize legal procedures and accelerate implementation. However, private parties have shown limited engagement, largely due to fragmented public governance, rigid administrative procedures, and a lack of a shared strategic framework for adaptation, which disconnects national strategies from local realities. The private sector is underrepresented due to a lack of awareness regarding climate change adaptation, perceived low profitability, high risk, and projects often failing to meet financial criteria for return on investment or guarantees. Economic barriers include high unemployment and poverty, reducing local capacity to manage finance, and a preference for traditional debt over green infrastructure investments. There's also a significant lack of local expertise in project development and financial engineering, hindering the creation of bankable climate projects and the navigation of complex funding schemes. Despite these challenges, opportunities exist through available European and national funding, a favorable political context, and legal tools that allow for delegation of funds and co-financing models. The FLAG can mobilize private capital by leveraging public-private partnerships with financial mechanisms like guarantees and prefinancing, and promising sectors include sustainable tourism, local food production, and agroecology. The report suggests that a robust sustainability framework with measurable outcomes, supported by AI and smart contracts, could enhance transparency and attract ESG-focused investors, ultimately aiming to reduce transaction costs and foster direct relationships between private stakeholders and adaptation providers.

5 Overarching lessons learned bankability reports

The collaborative development of the bankability reports uncover various hurdles, some could be overcome while others could not. In this final section we reflect on our initial research question **‘How can we attract private investors to support climate change adaptation solutions?’** and describe the lessons learned, derived from both the local stakeholder interviews and collected during the workshops. The lessons learned focus on the ‘supply side’ of providing bankable adaptation infrastructure projects, and the barriers and opportunities that were met throughout the process. Overall, the bankability reports can be considered as planted seeds, that require further nurturing to become sustainable long-term bankable adaptation projects.

1. Bankability as an integral part of the adaptation planning and development process

Although the adaptation solutions in each of the demonstrators followed their own timeline, considering bankability and the possibility of involving private investors was considered a valuable contribution. Considering bankability in the earlier stages of solution development often resulted in identifying additional solution beneficiaries, who had not yet been involved as key community stakeholders (both public and private stakeholders). Identifying these additional stakeholders led to discussions on beneficiaries providing adaptation funding and through what type of instruments this could be done. Additionally, identifying a variety of water-related beneficiaries (both up- and downstream, as well as the value chain) potentially lead to a variety of instruments to capture benefits resulting in more diverse revenue streams, ultimately facilitating long-term sustainable funding.

2. Involving private investors and tailoring the match-making

In most demonstrators developing bankable projects and involving private investors was met with apprehension and uncertainty. Public funding through grants or general budget allocations are better known and feel more comfortable, with many demonstrators indicating that adaptation solutions are often public infrastructure and should therefore be financed through public budgets. Furthermore, a lack of knowledge and capacity to develop bankable projects is a hindering factor to involve private investors. The fact that the use of funding and financing mechanisms is very context dependent and related to country specific fiscal and other regulatory frameworks, makes it challenging to generalize an approach. Developing sustainably bankable adaptation projects requires a tailored approach appropriate to the context, in which there is sufficient knowledge on both the development of adaptation projects, and the financial and fiscal context.

Additionally, demonstrators tend to work in a project-by-project approach as opposed to a more programmatic or ‘portfolio’ approach in which projects are combined and collectively developed. Such an approach would both upscale and accelerate the development of adaptation solutions, moreover a scaled-up approach could develop more interest from private investors as they often require a minimum scale of investment (ca. upwards of 1 million euro). However, in many demonstrators (e.g. Galicia, WRT, Guadeloupe), the funding/financing can be organized locally between providers and beneficiaries, ensuring that the local benefits and developed revenues remain in the community.

3. Data availability

The bankability reports which were developed towards the end of TransformAr, remain largely exploratory due to a lack of detailed data on investment costs, and potential avoided costs. This timing limited the availability of reliable cost information and made it difficult to assess avoided costs beyond identifying general areas of risk reduction, which are not easily quantified. Moreover, while the benefits of ecosystem services are highly context dependent, the absence of local evidence required reliance on international literature. Based on the development process within TransformAr, we would highly recommend considering bankability and governance related to bankability at the start of adaptation planning.

6 References

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7 Annex 1: Bankability report Lappeenranta, FI

8 Annex 2: Bankability report Egaleo, GR

9 Annex 3: Bankability report Galicia, SP

10Annex 4: Bankability report West Country Region, UK

11Annex 5: Bankability report Oristano, IT

12Annex 6: Bankability report Guadeloupe, FR

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

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